

Chemical and **B**iopharmaceutical **T**echnologies

collection of scientific
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V. Bessarabov, V. Lubenets

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CHEMICAL AND BIOPHARMACEUTICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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The collection of scientific works is devoted to the current problems of development, research and production of active pharmaceutical ingredients, medicinal and cosmetic products, fundamental and applied physical and organic chemistry, molecular pharmacology and chemogenomics, ecology, toxicology and pharmaceutical technology, technology of polymer and composite materials, marketing research in the field pharmacy and pharmaceutical production organizations. The collection contains abstracts of reports and research articles that were presented as part of the VI International Scientific and Practical Conference "KyivLvivPharma-2023. Pharmaceutical Technology and Pharmacology in Ensuring Active Longevity" (November 16-18, 2023, Kyiv, Lviv). This collection of scientific works is the direct successor of the collection of scientific works "PHYSICAL ORGANIC CHEMISTRY, PHARMACOLOGY AND PHARMACEUTICAL TECHNOLOGY OF BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES", which was published annually from 2017 to 2021.

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Section 5 Ecological, marketing and economic aspects of the industrial production of drugs and cosmetics, functionalized foods for the elderly.

MARKETING ASPECTS OF PROVIDING FUNCTIONALIZED FOOD PRODUCTS FOR ELDERLY PEOPLE

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Functionalized food products for the elderly are aimed at meeting the special needs and requirements of this population group. Elderly people may have certain physiological, dietary and nutritional restrictions, and require special products to ensure optimal health and living comfort. Also, functional foods must be tasty and attractive to consumers in order to stimulate appetite and improve their eating habits. Ease of opening a package for older people can be an important consideration when choosing a product. It is important to consider possible allergies and other aspects of product safety for this group of consumers.

Designers must take these factors into account when creating functional products that take into account the unique needs and requirements of older adults.

The purpose of the study: to analyze the presence of functionalized drinks for the elderly on the pharmaceutical market of Ukraine.

Research materials and methods. Experimental material, scientific articles, official Internet pages. The research used methods of marketing analysis, structural-functional, comparison method, generalization method and content analysis.

Research results. Elderly people may need special nutrition for various reasons, such as a decrease in muscle mass, deterioration of dental health, the development of osteoporosis, decreased appetite, digestive problems, and others.

Given the potential digestive issues in the elderly, functionalized foods can include easily digestible ingredients and help support healthy gastrointestinal function.

Various probiotic products for the elderly are available on the Ukrainian market. Here are some typical probiotic foods that can be found:

- probiotic yogurts and kefir: Many manufacturers offer yogurts and kefir that contain live cultures of probiotics. These foods may be useful for maintaining gastrointestinal health. Elderly people are able to improve the condition of diarrhea that occurs after taking antibiotics. Also, their use can improve the condition of irritable bowel syndrome.
- probiotic drinks (kombucha, narine, ayran): contain beneficial bacteria that help maintain a healthy intestinal microflora.
- probiotic soups and juices: some manufacturers include probiotics in soups and juices, which can be useful for varying probiotic intake.

- probiotic sachets, powders, capsules, tablets: pharmacies offer probiotic products that are specially designed to support health if there are certain medical problems or dietary restrictions.

- probiotic products for diabetics and lactose-free products: some manufacturers can create probiotic products that take into account dietary restrictions, such as low sugar content for diabetics, as well as allergic reactions to milk lactose.

The assortment and brands of probiotic products of manufacturers in Ukraine may change over time, so it is important to follow market updates and study the information on product packaging to confirm the presence of probiotics and their amount in a specific product.

It has been shown that the administration of probiotics has a beneficial effect on well-being, the state of intestinal microflora, and the immune status of the elderly. Regular consumption of probiotic products is believed to support a lifestyle aimed at longevity.

Studies show the promising use of probiotics for the prevention of osteoporosis. According to researchers from the University of Gothenburg, elderly people should take probiotics to preserve their bones. New evidence suggests that probiotic treatment may be an effective and safe way to prevent the onset of osteoporosis in older adults. With the help of computer tomography, the scientists assessed the levels of bone mass loss in the lower limbs at the beginning and at the end of the experiment. It was found that the women who took the probiotics lost half as much bone mass as the placebo control group.

We studied a probiotic that contained the bacteria *Limosilactobacillus reuteri*, preparations based on it have a wide spectrum of biological action and are widely used in the pharmaceutical, food and veterinary industries abroad, however, the Ukrainian production of probiotic supplements based on this species is not established, despite all the prospects of using this species in similar branches of the economy of Ukraine and the corresponding economic effect from the implementation of such production.

Conclusions.

The development of products with increased functionality intended for consumption by the elderly, which take into account their physiology and age and contribute to the reduction of the probability of age-related diseases, is a key aspect of solving the tasks of extending the active period of life of the aging population. This requires collaboration between medical professionals, nutritionists and technologists to achieve optimal results.

PROSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS OF DOMESTIC CANNABIS-BASED MEDICINES DEVELOPMENT

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These results demonstrated that bis(thiazol-5-yl)phenylmethane derivatives **23a** and **28b** could be potentially explored as scaffolds for the development of novel candidates targeting drug-resistant *S. aureus*.

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EVALUATION OF ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE IN *LIMOSILACTOBACILLUS REUTERI* AND *LACTOBACILLUS ACIDOPHILUS* FOR PROBIOTIC DIETARY SUPPLEMENT DEVELOPMENT

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Antibiotic resistance poses a significant concern in modern healthcare, often leading to gastrointestinal (GIT) disorders and necessitating effective treatment options. Probiotic dietary supplements have emerged as a common approach to address these disorders. However, safety regulations mandate that probiotic strains used in such supplements should not harbor antibiotic resistance plasmids.

The purpose of the work. In our study, we focused on the development of a probiotic dietary supplement utilizing *Limosilactobacillus reuteri* and *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. To evaluate their antibiotic resistance profiles, we conducted an antibiotic sensitivity test using the modified disk diffusion method.

Materials and methods. The antibiotics tested included vancomycin, benzylpenicillin, ristomycin, chloramphenicol, and oxacillin, each at a concentration of 15 mg per disk. Bacterial inoculum was prepared by diluting a bacterial culture in saline to match a 1 McFarland turbidity standard. One cubic centimeter of the inoculum was evenly spread over the surface of wort-agar medium within Petri dishes. Antibiotic disks were then placed on the inoculated plates. This procedure was repeated three times for each bacterial species to ensure the accuracy of the results. The test plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Results and discussions. The obtained results are shown in table 1.

Table 1

Antibiotic	<i>Lm. reuteri</i>		<i>L. acidophilus</i>	
	Zone of growth retradition of the microorganism, mm	Sensibility	Zone of growth retradition of the microorganism, mm	Sensibility
Vancomycin	24±14	Very sensitive	19±2	Sensitive
Benzylpenicillin	5±1	Not sensitive	0	Not sensitive
Ristomycin	24±4	Very sensitive	15±1	Sensitive
Chloramphenicol	20±4	Very sensitive	25±1	Very sensitive
Oxacillin	24±7	Sensitive	15±11	Not sensitive

Our study revealed that both *Lm. reuteri* and *L. acidophilus* displayed no significant antibiotic resistance, indicating their suitability as probiotic strains for supplement production.

Conclusions.

These findings contribute to the development of safer and more effective probiotic dietary supplements, addressing the growing concerns of antibiotic resistance and GIT disorders.

АНТИБІОТИКИ У ПРОФІЛАКТИЦІ ТА ЛІКУВАННІ НЕЙРОДЕГЕНЕРАТИВНИХ ЗАХВОРЮВАНЬ: ДОСЯГНЕННЯ ТА ПРОБЛЕМИ

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За даними ВООЗ, нейродегенеративні захворювання (НДЗ) широко поширені в усьому світі, зокрема нараховується понад 33 млн пацієнтів з хворобою Альцгеймера, та понад 6 млн осіб з хворобою Паркінсона. Хоча певні методи лікування полегшують деякі фізичні або психічні порушення, пов'язані з НДЗ, сповільнити їхню прогресію наразі неможливо, і радикальних ліків поки не існує. Однією зі стратегій вирішення цієї проблеми, яка набирає популярність, є таргетне перепрофілювання відомих препаратів, особливо антибіотичних, у тому числі біотехнологічного походження, які вже пройшли випробування на токсичність і клінічну безпеку.

Мета дослідження: здійснити мета-аналіз і підсумовуюче рев'ю останніх наукових публікацій щодо здобутків і перспектив використання антибіотиків у профілактиці та лікуванні НДЗ.

Матеріали і методи дослідження. Предметним полем аналітико-теоретичних досліджень була сукупність цільових наукових публікацій з